

$\pi g\beta$ -Normal Spaces in Topological Spaces

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Abstract: The aim of this paper is to introduce a new class of normal spaces called $\pi g\beta$ -normal spaces, by using $\pi g\beta$ -open sets. We prove that $\pi g\beta$ -normality is a topological property and it is a hereditary property with respect to π -open, $\pi g\beta$ -closed subspaces. Further we obtain a characterization and preservation theorems for $\pi g\beta$ -normal spaces.

Keywords: regular closed, π -closed, $\pi g\beta$ -closed, and β -open sets; pre β -closed, π -continuous, $\pi g\beta$ -continuous, π -irresolute, $\pi g\beta$ -irresolute and almost β -irresolute functions; $\pi g\beta$ -normal spaces

1. Introduction

In 1970, Levine [7] defined generalized closed sets in topological spaces. In 1989, Nour [9] introduced the notion of p -normal spaces and obtained characterization and preservation theorems for p -normal spaces. In 1990, Mahmoud and Monsef [8] introduced the concept of β -normal spaces. In 1995, Dontchev [5] introduced a new class of sets called $g\beta$ -closed sets. In 2010, Tahiliani [10] introduced the notion of $\pi g\beta$ -closed sets and its properties are studied. Recently, Thanh and Thinh [12] introduced the notion of πgp -normal spaces and prove that πgp -normality is a topological property and it is a hereditary property with respect to π -open, πgp -closed subspaces.

In this paper, we introduce and study a new class of normal spaces called $\pi g\beta$ -normal spaces by using $\pi g\beta$ -open sets. We prove that $\pi g\beta$ -normality is a topological property and it is a hereditary property with respect to π -open, $\pi g\beta$ -closed subspaces. Further we obtain a characterization and preservation theorems for $\pi g\beta$ -normal spaces

2. Preliminaries

Throughout this paper, spaces (X, τ) , (Y, σ) , and (Z, γ) always mean topological spaces on which no separation axioms are assumed unless explicitly stated. Let A be a subset of a space X . The closure of A and interior of A are denoted by $cl(A)$ and $int(A)$ respectively. A subset A is said to be **regular open** [6] (resp. **regular closed** [6]) if $A = int(cl(A))$ (resp. $A = cl(int(A))$). The finite union of regular open sets is said to be **π -open** [15]. The complement of a π -open set is said to be **π -closed** [15]. A is said to be **β -open** [1] if $A \subset cl(int(cl(A)))$. The family of all β -open sets of X is denoted by $\beta O(X)$. The complement of a β -open set is said to be **β -closed** [1]. The intersection of all β -closed sets containing A is called **β -closure** [2] of A , and is denoted by $\beta cl(A)$. The **β -Interior** [2] of A , denoted by $\beta int(A)$, is defined as union of all β -open sets contained in A . It is well known $\beta cl(A) = A \cup int(cl(int(A)))$ and $\beta int(A) = A \cap cl(int(cl(A)))$.

2.1 Definition

A subset A of a space X is said to be

- (1) **generalized closed** (briefly **g -closed**) [7] if $cl(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and $U \in \tau$.
- (2) **generalized β -closed** (briefly **$g\beta$ -closed**) [5] if $\beta cl(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and $U \in \tau$.
- (3) **$\pi g\beta$ -closed** [10] if $\beta cl(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and U is π -open in X .
- (4) **g -open** (resp. **$g\beta$ -open**, **$\pi g\beta$ -open**) if the complement of A is g -closed (resp. $g\beta$ -closed, $\pi g\beta$ -closed).

The intersection of all $\pi g\beta$ -closed sets containing A is called **$\pi g\beta$ -closure** of A , and is denoted by $\pi g\beta cl(A)$. The **$\pi g\beta$ -interior** of A , denoted by $\pi g\beta int(A)$, is defined as union of all $\pi g\beta$ -open sets contained in A . The family of all $\pi g\beta$ -open (resp. $\pi g\beta$ -closed) sets of X is denoted by $\pi g\beta O(X)$ (resp. $\pi g\beta C(X)$).

2.2 Definition

A space X is said to be **β -normal** [8] (resp. **p -normal** [9]) if for every pair of disjoint closed subsets A, B of X , there exist disjoint β -open (resp. p -open) sets U, V of X such that $A \subset U$ and $B \subset V$

2.3 Definition

A space X is said to be **$\pi\beta$ -normal** [14] (resp. **πp -normal** [11]) if for every pair of disjoint closed subsets A, B of X , one of which is π -closed, there exist disjoint β -open (resp. p -open) sets U, V of X such that $A \subset U$ and $B \subset V$.

2.4 Definition

A subset A of a space X is said to be a β -neighborhood [8] of x if there exists a β -open set U such that $x \in U \subset A$.

2.5 Definition. A function $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is said to be

- (a) **regular open** [13] if $f(U)$ is regular open in Y for every open set U in X .

- (b) π -continuous [4] if $f^{-1}(F)$ is π -closed in X for each closed set F in Y .
- (c) **pre- β -closed** [8] (resp. **pre β -open** [8]) $f(F)$ is β -closed (resp. β -open) set in for every β -closed (resp. β -open) set F in X .
- (d) **$\pi g\beta$ -continuous** [10] if $f^{-1}(F)$ is $\pi g\beta$ -closed in X for every closed set F in Y .
- (e) **$\pi g\beta$ -irresolute** [10] if $f^{-1}(F)$ is $\pi g\beta$ -closed in X for every $\pi g\beta$ -closed set F in Y .
- (f) **almost β -irresolute** [8] if for each $x \in X$ and β -neighborhood V of $f(x)$ in Y , $\beta cl(f^{-1}(V))$ is neighborhood of x in X .

3. $\pi g\beta$ -Normal Spaces

In this section, we introduce the notion of $\pi g\beta$ -normal space and study some property of it. First, we begin with the following definitions and examples.

3.1 Definition

A space X is said to be **$\pi g\beta$ -normal** (resp. **πgp -normal** [12]) if for every pair of disjoint $\pi g\beta$ -closed (resp. πgp -closed) subsets H and K of X , there exist disjoint β -open (resp. p -open) sets U, V of X such that $H \subset U$ and $K \subset V$.

Clearly, from above definitions, we have the following diagram:

Where none of the above implications is reversible as can be seen from the following examples:

3.2 Example

We consider the topology $\tau = \{\emptyset, \{b, d\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{b, c, d\}, X\}$ on the set $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$. Then, the space X is p -normal as well as β -normal. But it is neither πgp -normal nor $\pi g\beta$ -normal.

3.3 Example

Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$ and $\tau = \{\emptyset, \{b\}, \{d\}, \{b, d\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{b, c, d\}, X\}$. Then the space X is β -normal as well as $\pi\beta$ -normal but it is not p -normal.

3.4 Example

Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$ and $\tau = \{\emptyset, \{a\}, \{c\}, \{a, c\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{b, c, d\}, X\}$. The pair of disjoint closed subsets of X are $A = \{a\}$ and $B = \{c\}$. Also $U = \{a, b\}$ and $V = \{c, d\}$ are β -open sets such that $A \subset U$ and $B \subset V$. Hence X is β -normal as well as $\pi\beta$ -normal.

3.5 Example

Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$ and $\tau = \{\emptyset, \{a\}, \{b, d\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{b, c, d\}, X\}$. Then, the space X is β -normal.

3.6 Theorem

For a topological space X , the following are equivalent:

- (a) X is $\pi g\beta$ -normal.
- (b) For every pair of disjoint $\pi g\beta$ -open subsets U and V of X whose union is X , there exist β -closed subsets G and H of X such that $G \subset U, H \subset V$ and $G \cup H = X$.
- (c) For every $\pi g\beta$ -closed set A and every $\pi g\beta$ -open set B in X such that $A \subset B$, there exists a β -open subset V of X such that $A \subset V \subset \beta cl(V) \subset B$.
- (d) For every pair of disjoint $\pi g\beta$ -closed subsets A and B of X , there exists a β -open subset V of X such that $A \subset V$ and $\beta cl(V) \cap B = \emptyset$.
- (e) For every pair of disjoint $\pi g\beta$ -closed subsets A and B of X , there exist β -open subsets U and V of X such that $A \subset U, B \subset V$ and $\beta cl(U) \cap \beta cl(V) = \emptyset$.

Proof

- (a) \Rightarrow (b), (b) \Rightarrow (c), (c) \Rightarrow (d), (d) \Rightarrow (e) and (e) \Rightarrow (a).
- (a) \Rightarrow (b) Let U and V be any $\pi g\beta$ -open subsets of a $\pi g\beta$ -normal space X such that $U \cup V = X$. Then, $X \setminus U$ and $X \setminus V$ are disjoint $\pi g\beta$ -closed subsets of X . By $\pi g\beta$ -normality of X , there exist disjoint β -open subsets U_1 and V_1 of X such that $X \setminus U \subset U_1$ and $X \setminus V \subset V_1$. Let $G = X \setminus U_1$ and $H = X \setminus V_1$. Then, G and H are β -closed subsets in X such that $G \cup H = X$.
- (b) \Rightarrow (c). Let A be a $\pi g\beta$ -closed and B is $\pi g\beta$ -open subsets of X such that $A \subset B$. Then, $A \cap (X \setminus B) = \emptyset$. Thus, $X \setminus A$ and B are $\pi g\beta$ -open subsets of X such that $(X \setminus A) \cup B = X$. By the Part (b), there exist β -closed subsets G and H of X such that $G \subset (X \setminus A), H \subset B$ and $G \cup H = X$. Thus, we obtain that $A \subset (X \setminus G) \subset H \subset B$. Let $V = X \setminus G$. Then V is β -open subset of X and $\beta cl(V) \subset H$ as H is β -closed set in X . Therefore, $A \subset V \subset \beta cl(V) \subset B$.
- (c) \Rightarrow (d). Let A and B be disjoint $\pi g\beta$ -closed subset of X . Then $A \subset X \setminus B$, where $X \setminus B$ is $\pi g\beta$ -open. By the part (c), there exists a β -open subset U of X such that $A \subset U \subset \beta cl(U) \subset X \setminus B$. Thus, $\beta cl(U) \cap B = \emptyset$.
- (d) \Rightarrow (e). Let A and B be any disjoint $\pi g\beta$ -closed subset of X . Then by the part (d), there exists a β -open set U containing A such that $\beta cl(U) \cap B = \emptyset$. Since $\beta cl(U)$ is β -closed, then it is $\pi g\beta$ -closed. Thus $\beta cl(U)$ and B are disjoint $\pi g\beta$ -closed subsets of X . Again by the part (d), there exists a β -open set V in X such that $B \subset V$ and $\beta cl(U) \cap \beta cl(V) = \emptyset$.
- (e) \Rightarrow (a). Let A and B be any disjoint $\pi g\beta$ -closed subsets of X . Then by the part (e), there exist β -open sets U and V such that $A \subset U, B \subset V$ and $\beta cl(U) \cap \beta cl(V) = \emptyset$. Therefore, we obtain that $U \cap V = \emptyset$ and hence X is $\pi g\beta$ -normal.

3.7 Lemma

- (a) The image of β -open subset under an open continuous function is β -open.
 (b) The inverse image of β -open (resp. β -closed) subset under an open continuous function is β -open (resp. β -closed) subset.

3.8 Lemma [12]

The image of a regular open subset under open and closed continuous function is regular open subset.

3.9 Proposition [12]

The image of a π -open subset under open and closed continuous function is π -open set.

3.10 Proposition

If $f : X \rightarrow Y$ be an open and closed continuous bijection function and A be a $\pi\gamma\beta$ -closed set in Y , then $f^{-1}(A)$ is $\pi\gamma\beta$ -closed set in X .

Proof. Let A be a $\pi\gamma\beta$ -closed subset of Y and U be any π -open subset of X such that $f^{-1}(A) \subset U$. Then by the **Proposition 3.9**, we have $f(U)$ is π -open subset of Y such that $A \subset f(U)$. Since A is $\pi\gamma\beta$ -closed subset of Y and $f(U)$ is π -open set in Y , thus $\beta\text{cl}(A) \subset U$. By the **Lemma 3.7**, we obtain that $f^{-1}(A) \subset f^{-1}(\beta\text{cl}(A)) \subset U$, where $f^{-1}(\beta\text{cl}(A))$ is β -closed in X . This implies that $\beta\text{cl}(f^{-1}(A)) \subset U$. Therefore, $f^{-1}(A)$ is $\pi\gamma\beta$ -closed set in X .

3.11 Theorem. $\pi\gamma\beta$ -normality is a topological property.

Proof. Let X be a $\pi\gamma\beta$ -normal space and $f : X \rightarrow Y$ be an open and closed bijection continuous function. We need to show that Y is $\pi\gamma\beta$ -normal. Let A and B be any disjoint $\pi\gamma\beta$ -closed subsets of Y . Then by the **Proposition 3.10**, $f^{-1}(A)$ and $f^{-1}(B)$ are disjoint of $\pi\gamma\beta$ -closed subsets of X . By $\pi\gamma\beta$ -normality of X , there exist β -open subsets U and V of X such that $f^{-1}(A) \subset U$, $f^{-1}(B) \subset V$ and $U \cap V = \emptyset$. By assumption, we have $A \subset f(U)$, $B \subset f(V)$ and $f(U) \cap f(V) = \emptyset$. By the **Lemma 3.7**, $f(U)$ and $f(V)$ are disjoint β -open subsets of Y such that $A \subset f(U)$ and $B \subset f(V)$. Hence, Y is $\pi\gamma\beta$ -normal.

4. $\pi\gamma\beta$ -normality in subspaces

4.1 Lemma. If M be an open subspace of a space X and $A \subset M$, then $\beta\text{cl}_M(A) = \beta\text{cl}_X(A) \cap M$.

4.2 Lemma [12]. If M be an open subspace of a space X and $A \subset M$, then $\text{int}_M(\text{cl}_M(A)) = \text{int}_X(\text{cl}_X(A)) \cap M$.

4.3 Lemma [12]. If M be a π -open subspace of a space X and U be a π -open subset of X , then $U \cap M$ is π -open set in M .

4.4 Lemma. If A is both π -open and $\pi\gamma\beta$ -closed subset of a space X , then A is β -closed set in X .

Proof. Since A is $\pi\gamma\beta$ -closed and π -open subset of X and since $A \subset A$, then $\beta\text{cl}(A) \subset A$. But $A \subset \beta\text{cl}(A)$. Thus, $A = \beta\text{cl}(A)$. Hence, A is β -closed set in X .

4.5 Corollary. If A is both π -open and $\pi\gamma\beta$ -closed subset of a space X , then A is regular closed set in X .

4.6 Theorem. Let M be a π -open subspace of a space X and $A \subset M$. If M is $\pi\gamma\beta$ -closed set in X and A is $\pi\gamma\beta$ -closed set in M . Then A is $\pi\gamma\beta$ -closed set in X .

Proof. Suppose that M is $\pi\gamma\beta$ -closed set in X and A is $\pi\gamma\beta$ -closed set in M . Let U be any π -open set in X such that $A \subset U$. Then by **Lemma 4.3**, we have $A \subset M \cap U$, where $M \cap U$ is π -open set in M . Since A is $\pi\gamma\beta$ -closed in M , thus $\beta\text{cl}_M(A) \subset M \cap U$. The by the **Lemma 4.1**, $\beta\text{cl}_X(A) \cap M \subset M \cap U$. By the **Lemma 4.4**, we obtain that $\beta\text{cl}_X(M) = M$. Thus, $\beta\text{cl}_X(A) \subset \beta\text{cl}_X(M) = M$. So, $\beta\text{cl}_X(A) \cap M = \beta\text{cl}_X(A)$. Hence, $\beta\text{cl}_X(M) \subset U \cap M$. Thus, $\beta\text{cl}_X(A) \subset U$. Therefore, A is $\pi\gamma\beta$ -closed set in X .

4.7 Lemma. Let M be a closed domain subspace of a space X . If U is β -open set in X , then $U \cap M$ is β -open set in M .

4.8 Theorem. A $\pi\gamma\beta$ -closed and π -open subspace of a $\pi\gamma\beta$ -normal space is $\pi\gamma\beta$ -normal.

Proof. Let M be a $\pi\gamma\beta$ -closed and π -open subspace of a $\pi\gamma\beta$ -normal space X . Let A and B be any disjoint $\pi\gamma\beta$ -closed subsets of M . Then by **Theorem 4.6**, we have A and B are disjoint $\pi\gamma\beta$ -closed sets in X . By $\pi\gamma\beta$ -normality of X , there exist β -open subsets U and V of X such that $A \subset U$, $B \subset V$ and $U \cap V = \emptyset$. By the **Corollary 4.5** and **Lemma 4.7**, we obtain that $U \cap M$ and $V \cap M$ are disjoint β -open sets in M such that $A \subset U \cap M$ and $B \subset V \cap M$. Hence, M is $\pi\gamma\beta$ -normal subspace of $\pi\gamma\beta$ -normal space X .

5. Preservation theorems for $\pi\gamma\beta$ -Normality

5.1 Definition

A function $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is said to be π -irresolute [3] if $f^{-1}(F)$ is π -closed in X for every π -closed set F in Y .

5.2 Theorem

If $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is π -irresolute, pre β -closed and A is a $\pi\gamma\beta$ -closed subset of X , then $f(A)$ is $\pi\gamma\beta$ -closed subset of Y .

Proof. Let A be a $\pi\gamma\beta$ -closed subset of X and U be any π -open set of Y such that $f(A) \subset U$. Then, $A \subset f^{-1}(U)$. Since f is π -irresolute function, then $f^{-1}(U)$ is π -open in X . Since A is $\pi\gamma\beta$ -closed set in X and $A \subset f^{-1}(U)$, then $\beta\text{cl}_X(A) \subset f^{-1}(U)$. This implies that $f(\beta\text{cl}_X(A)) \subset U$. Since f is pre β -closed and $\beta\text{cl}_X(A)$ is β -closed set in X , then $f(\beta\text{cl}_X(A))$ is β -closed in Y . Thus, we have $\beta\text{cl}_Y(f(A)) \subset U$. Hence, $f(A)$ is $\pi\gamma\beta$ -closed subset of Y .

5.3 Corollary

If $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is π -continuous, pre β -closed and A is a $\pi g\beta$ -closed subset of X , then $f(A)$ is $\pi g\beta$ -closed subset of Y .

5.4 Theorem

If $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is π -irresolute, pre β -closed and β -irresolute injection function from a space X to a $\pi g\beta$ -normal Y , then X is $\pi g\beta$ -normal.

Proof. Let A and B be any two disjoint $\pi g\beta$ -closed subsets of X . By the **Theorem 5.2** $f(A)$ and $f(B)$ are disjoint $\pi g\beta$ -closed subsets of Y . By $\pi g\beta$ -normality of Y , there exist disjoint β -open subsets U and V of Y such that $f(A) \subset U$, $f(B) \subset V$ and $U \cap V = \emptyset$. Since f is β -irresolute injection function, then $f^{-1}(U)$ and $f^{-1}(V)$ are disjoint β -open sets in X such that $A \subset f^{-1}(U)$ and $B \subset f^{-1}(V)$. Hence X is $\pi g\beta$ -normal.

5.5 Corollary

If $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is π -continuous, pre β -closed and β -irresolute injection function from a space X to a $\pi g\beta$ -normal Y , then X is $\pi g\beta$ -normal.

5.6 Lemma

If the bijection function $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is β -continuous and regular open, then f is $\pi g\beta$ -irresolute.

5.7 Theorem

If $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is $\pi g\beta$ -irresolute, pre β -closed bijection function from a $\pi g\beta$ -normal space X to a space Y , then Y is $\pi g\beta$ -normal.

Proof. Let A and B be any two disjoint $\pi g\beta$ -closed subsets of Y . Since f is $\pi g\beta$ -irresolute, we have $f^{-1}(A)$ and $f^{-1}(B)$ are disjoint $\pi g\beta$ -closed subsets of X . By $\pi g\beta$ -normality of X , there exist disjoint β -open sets U and V in X such that $f^{-1}(A) \subset U$, $f^{-1}(B) \subset V$ and $U \cap V = \emptyset$. Since f is pre β -open and bijection function, we have $f(U)$ and $f(V)$ are disjoint β -open sets in Y such that $A \subset f(U)$, $B \subset f(V)$ and $f(U) \cap f(V) = \emptyset$. Therefore, X is $\pi g\beta$ -normal.

5.8 Corollary

If $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is β -continuous, regular open and pre β -open bijection function from a $\pi g\beta$ -normal space X to a space Y , then Y is $\pi g\beta$ -normal.

5.9 Theorem

If $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is a pre β -open, $\pi g\beta$ -irresolute and almost β -irresolute surjection function from a $\pi g\beta$ -normal space X onto a space Y , then Y is $\pi g\beta$ -normal.

Proof. Let A be a $\pi g\beta$ -closed subset of Y and B be a $\pi g\beta$ -open subset of Y such that $A \subset B$. Since f is $\pi g\beta$ -irresolute, we obtain that $f^{-1}(A)$ is $\pi g\beta$ -closed in X and $f^{-1}(B)$ is $\pi g\beta$ -open in X such that $f^{-1}(A) \subset f^{-1}(B)$. Since X is $\pi g\beta$ -normal, then by the Part (c) of the **Theorem 3.6**, there exists a β -open set U of X such that $f^{-1}(A) \subset U \subset \beta cl_X(U) \subset f^{-1}(B)$. Then, $f(f^{-1}(A)) \subset f(U) \subset f(\beta cl_X(f(U))) \subset f(f^{-1}(B))$. Since f is pre β -open, almost β -irresolute surjection, we obtain that $A \subset f(U) \subset \beta cl_Y(f(U)) \subset B$ and $f(U)$ is β -open set in Y . Hence by the **Theorem 3.6**, we have Y is $\pi g\beta$ -normal.

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